

Transport Sectors' Real-World Emissions: From Gaseous Precursors to Secondary Aerosol Formation in Urban Air

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Abstract. Mobility is essential to our modern world to move people and goods. However, mobility has also its downside as transport sectors are substantial emitters of greenhouse gases and air pollutants. Increasingly energy efficient combustion engines and turbines, as well as electrification and carbon-neutral fuels, will reduce the climate impacts of transportation. When such technologies are combined with advanced exhaust after-treatment technologies, air pollution impacts will also be reduced. Many exhaust emissions are already regulated regionally or globally, while actions to prevent the formation of secondary aerosols from emitted gaseous precursors in the atmosphere are missing. To increase understanding on the role of transport sectors' exhaust emissions on the secondary aerosol formation and to identify gaps in the knowledge, we present a summary of semi-volatile compounds, secondary air pollutants, ultrafine particle and particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) emissions. Non-exhaust emissions are also considered. The results are based on the PAREMPI project's emission database based on a literature review and new results from the projects' ongoing research activities.

Keywords: Exhaust Emissions · Particles · Secondary Aerosols · Toxicity · Health impact · Transport Sectors

1 Introduction

Mobility plays a vital role in our modern society, facilitating the movement of people and goods to meet our various needs, including those related to food, energy, and essential resources. However, it's essential to acknowledge that the transport sector comes with

its challenges, primarily associated with greenhouse gas emissions and air pollutants. While making strides in developing more energy-efficient combustion engines, adopting electrification, and exploring carbon-neutral fuels, these advancements are crucial for mitigating the climate impacts of transportation. In addition to addressing climate concerns, we must also consider the reduction of air pollution resulting from transportation. To achieve this, advanced technologies, such as exhaust after-treatment, are integrated into the transport sector. This is increasingly important in certain segments of the industry, such as aviation and maritime transportation, that present unique challenges in achieving full decarbonization through electrification alone. Many gaseous and particle emissions are already regulated as they are known to pose significant threats to health and global ecosystems as well as causing societal costs. However, transport emissions' role in the formation of secondary aerosols (SecA) in the atmosphere has not been taken into account.

In this context, we present a comprehensive overview of emissions from the transport sectors' emissions, focusing on (semi)-volatile organic compounds ((S)VOCs), secondary air pollutants, ultrafine particles (UFP), and particulate matter. Additionally, we consider non-exhaust emissions, broadening our perspective on the issue. Our findings are based on the extensive emission database, which is the result of an exhaustive literature review and ongoing research activities within the PAREMPI project. Throughout our discussion, we highlight the knowledge gaps that persist in our understanding of these exhaust emissions and their role in the secondary aerosol formation, emphasizing the need for specialized expertise to comprehensively evaluate and address these complex challenges. The results will assist further research to find solutions and initiate actions to prevent these emissions.

2 From Precursor Emissions to Secondary Aerosols

To approach discussion of secondary aerosols, we present definitions of aerosols, particles and secondary aerosols. By definition, aerosol is a suspension of gas with solid particles or liquid droplets originating either from natural (dust, volcanic ash etc.) or human-made processes (industry, vehicle exhaust etc.). Aerosols affect human health by entering into the respiratory system and even the bloodstream, and climate by scattering and absorbing solar radiation or by influences on cloud formation. Particulate matter (PM), constituent of aerosols, is described by World Health Organisation (WHO) as “*a mixture of solid and liquid particles in the air that are small enough not to settle out to the Earth surface*”. Important features of particles are their mass, size and number emissions. Ambient PM_{2.5} is a mass-based definition for particles having aerodynamic diameter below 2.5 μm , while combustion originated particles are small, below 1 μm or even nanometers in diameter and hence included in PM_{2.5}, while e.g. sea salt, geological dust, biogenic PM and residual ash tend to be in the larger size range than PM_{2.5}. Small particle sizes may have low mass, but still substantial adverse health effects caused by high number of ultrafine particles (<0.1 μm) and nanoparticles (<50 nm). Hence, particle exhaust emissions are defined also by their number and lung deposited surface area [1]. In the European emission standards, number of non-volatile particles (nvPN) are included, currently those with diameter above 23 nm [2], and smaller particles above

10 nm are proposed to be included [3]. For atmospheric and health aspects, total number of particles is considered, including also volatile particles and those below 10 nm, since these particles may carry for example harmful polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) [1, 4, 5].

Secondary aerosol form via secondary reactions of gas-phase precursors in the atmosphere under presence of H_2O , O_2 , oxidants (OH , O_3) and sunlight besides aerosol emitted directly into the atmosphere from biogenic or anthropogenic sources. For secondary reactions, combustion of carbonaceous fuels contributes by emitting precursor gases, such as sulphur oxides (SO_x), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ammonia (NH_3), as well as organic and inorganic aerosols (e.g. (S)VOCs, metals, salts, acids) and black carbon (BC) depending on fuel constituents, engine and aftertreatment technologies [1, 2]. SecA is further divided in secondary organic aerosol (SOA) and inorganic aerosol (SIA) [6, 7]. SOA formation involves nucleation, the partitioning of organic gases onto existing aerosol particles or reactions of primary OA and even the photosensitized chemistry is proposed leading to autocatalytic formation of SOA [8]. Aromatic compounds contribute significantly to the formation of SOA and faster than thought via molecular rearrangement of the bicyclic peroxy radicals (BPRs) leading to aerosol-forming low-volatility products [9]. SIA covers e.g. salts formed from metals, SO_2 or NH_3 .

Formation of SecA is complicated in the atmosphere where exhaust species mix and react with atmospheric compounds in local meteorological conditions (Fig. 1). Firstly, composition of exhaust varies depending on transport application, secondly the compounds present in atmosphere and their concentrations vary regionally, and thirdly, variable atmospheric conditions (e.g. meteorology, oxidants, UV) affect the reactions. For example, air quality is typically worst at low winter temperatures with low mixing height, however, dependences causing this phenomenon, and particularly the role of transport sectors' emissions, are not evidenced. Overall, ambient $PM_{2.5}$ accumulates from many sources, also those transported with air masses across borders, and apportionment of different sources in ambient $PM_{2.5}$ levels and its harmfulness is challenging.

Fig. 1. Exhaust emissions from variety of transport sources form SecA in the atmospheric reactions thus contributing to ambient $PM_{2.5}$ levels.

As secondary emissions form during the atmospheric aging process lasting from minutes to weeks, it is not possible to directly measure secondary aerosol formation. Therefore, SecA formation is typically characterized using oxidation flow reactors (OFRs) such as Potential Aerosol Mass (PAM; [10]) and Tampere Secondary Aerosol Reactor

(TSAR; [11]) chambers. The OFR is irradiated with UV light (of 185 and 254 nm) to form high concentrations of oxidants (O_3 , OH, HO_2) that can initiate SecA formation. High oxidant concentrations (up to 1000-fold to atmosphere with the same oxidant ratios as in the atmosphere) and intensive UV lights ensure fast oxidation of compounds. The aging as the sample flows through chamber is shown to represent from minutes to weeks aging in the atmosphere, depending on used oxidant amounts. After the PAM chamber, either PN concentrations, size distributions or composition of aerosols (including SecA) are typically measured either online with e.g. ELPI or aerosol mass spectrometers or offline from filter samples. The first widely available OFR (PAM) was developed by prof. Brune at Penn state university and first publication about the PAM chamber concept was published in 2007 by Kang et al. [10]. After that the amount of OFR publications has steadily increased and currently there are over 150 publications utilizing OFR in different laboratory and field studies.

3 Existing Data for Precursor Emissions and SecA

To understand the role of transport sector's emissions on the SecA, knowledge on the precursor emissions is necessary. Emission factors are available for basic emissions, SO_x , total hydrocarbons (HC), PM and NH_3 , for cars and heavy-duty vehicles [12], ships [13], and aircrafts [14] as presented in Table 1. Apparently, emission factors for ground-transport applications are low when compared with those for aircrafts and especially for ships. Less information is available for (semi-)volatile organic compounds e.g. benzene, toluene, PAHs, ultrafine particles, as well as formed SecA mass and its composition and toxicity, than for emission species presented in Table 1. In the continuation of work, a comparative analysis of emissions from different transport sectors will be refined.

Table 1. Examples of emission factors (EFs) for older cars, HDVs, ships and aircrafts.

Examples	SO_x g/kg fuel	HC/NMHC g/kg fuel	NO_x g/kg fuel	NH_3 g/kg fuel	PM g/kg fuel
Cars, petrol [12]	–	–/10.1	8.7	1.1	0.03
Cars, diesel [12]	–	–/0.7	13.0	0.065	1.1
HDVs [12]	–	–/1.9	33.4	0.013	0.9
Ships, diesel [13]	10.5	2.9/–	66.4	0	1.4
Aircrafts [14]	0.84	0.61/–	18	–	0.13

On-road: older fleets (Tier 1). Marine fuel < 0.5 wt% sulphur. Aviation: Airbus A-300B2.

Table 2 summarizes the availability of the results for the different transport sectors and shows that even for cars and heavy-duty vehicles (HDVs), relevant precursor emissions are sparsely reported in on-road real-driving (RDE) conditions. Many campaigns for measuring emissions from ships have been carried out, however, datasets are for single ships and for limited emissions species, e.g. (S)VOC data is almost non-existing. In the datasets, ships typically use residual or distillate marine fuels compliant with the

IMO's 0.5% sulphur limit (or 3.5% sulphur limit if scrubbers are used). More information is needed on the emissions for alternatives, such as LNG DF and methanol DF, or biofuels that are anticipated to enter market along with the IMO targets to cut GHG emissions of shipping to reach net-zero by 2050. For aviation sector, there are reports only on the basic emissions and limited data is available for the sustainable aviation fuels (SAF). Synthetic jet fuel (ASTM D7566) components are typically sulphur-free and low-aromatic, while final blends need to meet JET-A1 standard. More data than currently available is needed for precursor emissions from all transport sectors, and hence, new complementary measurements are needed to gather sufficient information.

The database and synthesis are needed for modelling and identifying different exhaust and SecA compositions [15]. For the database, we selected all the studies involving OFR measurements of transport emissions from different sectors (cars, HD vehicles, shipping, aviation). Altogether 21 publications with SecA emission factors for the transport exhaust emissions were identified.

Table 2. The major SecA related emission components for different transport sectors (Cars, HDVs, Shipping, Aviation) and the availability of measurement data.

Source	Existing data
Cars, HDVs	A few SecA studies. RDE data sparse for precursors and SecA
Shipping	Very few SecA studies. Measured data only for single ships
Aviation	No measured SecA data. Limited data for precursors

4 Conclusions

Analysis of the existing data showed that there are gaps in the knowledge of the transport sectors' precursor and secondary aerosol emissions, especially those measured in real-life, on-road conditions. This knowledge is essential to understand and model reactions and processes leading to formation of health impacting SecA due to atmospheric aerosol chemistry and for predicting SecA based on precursor emissions. In the continuation of the work presented here, complementary measurements will be carried out and toxicity of exhaust will be studied. With sufficient information on SecA emissions in combination with European level modelling, health impact assessment and improved quantification of externalities is possible. Scientific findings, together with tools and methodologies created, enable solid and well-justified policy considerations.

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